

A Host Property-Based Machine Learning Supernova Classifier

ADAM BOESKY ¹ AND ASHLEY VILLAR¹

¹*Center for Astrophysics | Harvard & Smithsonian, 60 Garden St., Cambridge, MA 02138, USA*

ABSTRACT

Recent astronomical surveys have offered a large number of wide-field observations which will grow exponentially as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory begins its decade-long Legacy Survey of Space and Time. It is well known that the properties of galaxies are correlated with the classes of supernovae (SNe) that they host, implying that astronomers can use host galaxy properties to aid in SN classification. A particularly useful case is classifying young SNe with their host properties, as little information can be extracted from the few photometric observations taken in their short lifetimes. We present a novel machine learning pipeline that classifies SNe using the spectral energy distributions (SEDs) of their host galaxies. We infer host stellar mass, star formation rate, and redshift from the host SEDs with a multilayer perceptron—a type of neural network. We then input these values and the host-supernova angular separation into a random forest (an ensemble learning method often used for classification) to produce a supernova classification. Our neural network infers galaxy properties quite well, producing $\log(M_*)$, $\log(\text{SFR})$, and redshift predictions with mean fractional errors of 0.133 and root-mean-squared errors of 0.621. These are reasonable given that the measured uncertainty to value ratios of our dataset are 0.40, 0.25, and 0.83 for $\log(M_*)$, $\log(\text{SFR})$, and redshift, respectively. Finally, our random forest performs comparably to other supernova classification methods, classifying type Ia SNe and other SNe with $\sim 97.5\%$ and $\sim 55\%$ purity, respectively, using 30% completeness. We believe that we can improve classification performance by expanding our dataset, which we plan to do in the coming weeks by conducting domain adaptation with galaxies from the Pan-STARRS catalog.

Keywords: Supernovae (1668), Classification (1907), Surveys (1671), Galaxies (573), Neural Networks (1933), Random Forests (1935)

1. INTRODUCTION

Supernovae (SNe) are astrophysically pivotal phenomena, serving as key elements in the cosmic cycle of matter and energy. These high-energy stellar explosions not only play a critical role in nucleosynthesis, generating and dispersing heavy elements essential for planetary formation, but also act as fundamental tools in probing cosmic distances and the expansion dynamics of the universe. Understanding and classifying supernovae, therefore, is not just a topic of stellar astrophysics, but it is an essential conduit to deciphering the evolutionary mechanisms of galaxies and the overarching structure of the Universe.

The Vera C. Rubin Observatory is set to begin the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) in the next few years, in which it is predicted to photometrically detect 1 million SNe per year (LSST Science Collaboration et al. 2009, SNe). While this unprecedented rate of supernova (SN) detection will vastly enrich the existing catalog of SNe, astrophysicists must take steps to prepare for the tens of thousands of transients captured each night—SN classification will be crucial to this effort.

SNe classification is an active field that has seen considerable changes in methodology in recent years. Historically, SNe have been classified using spectroscopy (Filippenko 1997). Spectroscopy, however, is highly expensive in terms of observational resources, which has caused astronomers to turn to photometric classification in recent years. When a SN is young, however, photometric classification is particularly poor due to the lack of information that we can glean from just a few days of photometric measurements. Luckily, SNe come from a wide variety of progenitor systems that imprint unique signatures on the SNe themselves. We may therefore be able to leverage known galaxy correlations to aid early classification, and therefore obtain cheap and accurate young SN class inferences.

Being able to confidently classify SNe shortly after they are detected would enable observational follow up of interesting SNe before they fade away. Observations of SNe early in their lives yield a plethora of interesting information such as mysterious peaks in luminosity of early superluminous SNe (Zhu et al. 2023) and signs of interaction with circumstellar material in type II core collapse SNe (e.g. SN 2023ixf analyzed in Bostroem et al. (2023)). Early spectroscopic observations are essential for analyzing these events, but scientists do not know which events to allocate observational resources to. Currently, due to instrumental constraints, only $\sim 1/10$ of transient phenomena detections are followed up spectroscopically (Kulkarni 2020); assuming that observational resources remain the same, this statistic will plummet to $\sim 1/500$ with onset of the LSST. Astronomy must therefore move away from the spectroscopic regime of classification in order to maximize the utility of detections. In particular, rapid, efficient, and accurate methods for classifying detections are preferred to maximize scientific discovery from massive catalogs.

In this paper, we present a machine learning pipeline for classifying SNe that uses multi-band photometry to predict properties of host galaxies and infer the most likely SN type based on these predicted properties. It is well known that host properties are strongly correlated with SN progenitor formation and evolution. Host galaxy properties should thus constrain the classes of SNe that they produce (Kisley et al. 2023; Kelly & Kirshner 2012) and possess sufficient information to confidently make classifications. We achieve this goal by constructing a pipeline consisting of a neural network that infers galaxy properties and a random forest that uses host properties to classify SNe.

While SN classification using host galaxy multi-band photometry *or* properties has been attempted before (e.g. Kisley et al. (2023) and Gagliano et al. (2021)) our pipeline is a novel unification of these methods, going from photometry to host properties, and then to SN class. The philosophical reasoning for this approach is two fold. First, the mapping between host spectral energy distribution (SED) and properties is a true, physical map, whereas the relationship between host SED and SN class is less direct. Therefore, using a neural network to “learn” the SED to property map, and then basing SN class inferences on the properties that physically influence SNe and progenitor physics, may be a more realistic, physically realisable pipeline, which could potentially lead to performance benefits. Second, inferring properties as an intermediary step will enable scientists to use our pipeline to focus on specific galaxy demographics. Given that our pipeline infers galaxy properties, one can make cuts in feature space to select for galaxies with high mass, low redshift, or any other such physical attributes.

Section 2.1 describes the dataset that we use, Section 2.2 through Section 2.3 describe the methodology of our pipeline, and Section 3 evaluates the performance of our pipeline using the metrics described in Section 2.4. Neural network accuracy is described in Section 3.1, where we compare host property predictions to true values. In Section 3.2 we assess our random forest classification using accuracy and purity metrics. Then, we discuss performance and future directions in Section 4. Finally, we conclude in Section 5.

2. METHODS

We present a machine learning pipeline that uses host galaxy SEDs to classify SNe. The structure of this methods section mimics that of our pipeline displayed in Figure 1: Section 2.1 describes our dataset, Section 2.1.3 is a summary of the host-SN association conducted with a cone search, Section 2.2 contains the structure and training of the neural network used to infer host properties, and Section 2.3 details how we implement a random forest to use the inferred properties to classify SNe.

2.1. Datasets

2.1.1. Host Galaxy Catalog

Zou et al. (2022) provides a catalog of multi-wavelength observations, SED fits, and derived properties for 2,873,803 galaxies. These galaxies are from W-CDF-S (4.9 deg^2), ELAIS-S1 (3.4 deg^2), and XMM-LSS (4.9 deg^2), three Deep-Drilling Fields deep drilling fields (DDFs) of the Vera C. Rubin Observatory LSST. The photometric observations are collected in a non-simultaneous manner from the following astronomical survey catalogs: Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX), VST Optical Imaging of the CDF-S and ELAIS-S1 Fields (VOICE), Hyper Suprime-Cam (HSC), VISTA Deep Extragalactic Observations (VIDEO), Spitzer Survey of Deep-Drilling Fields (DeepDrill), Spitzer Wide-area Infrared Extragalactic survey (SWIRE), and Dark Energy Survey (DES). We use photometric measurements from each galaxy in the following 18 bands/filters (which are ordered by ascending wavelength): g , r , i , z , y , J , H , K_s , $3.6 \mu\text{m}$, $4.5 \mu\text{m}$, MIPS24, MIPS70, PACS100, MIPS160, PACS160, SPIRE250, SPIRE350, SPIRE500. Zou et al. (2022) Table 2 provides the median wavelengths of these filters. See Zou et al. (2022) Table 1 for the galaxy demographics of the catalog, as well as the surveys and bands of the observations in each DDF.

Figure 1. Summary of the methods used in this paper. We feed host galaxy SED observations into a multilayer perception to infer host properties. We conduct a cone search to associate SNe with its host, and then use the inferred properties and host-SN angular separation in a random forest which classifies the SN. The classes of the supernovae that we infer are type Ia, Ib, Ic, II, and SLSN.

Zou et al. (2022) uses CIGALE (Yang et al. 2020) to fit source X-ray to far infrared SEDs in order to infer galaxy properties. Specifically, CIGALE is used to infer galactic stellar mass and star formation rate (SFR). Photometric redshifts (photo-zs) and spectroscopic redshifts (which are used when available) of the galaxies are compiled from Ni et al. (2021); Zou et al. (2021). In these studies, redshifts are derived using EAZY (Brammer et al. 2008) because the photo- z functionality in CIGALE is not yet very robust. Zou et al. (2021) also uses specially-tailored models for fitting the SEDs of galaxies that are promising candidates for containing an active galactic nucleus (AGN). For each galaxy, they fit them both as having and not having AGN, and estimate the probability that an AGN is present—we take the most likely of these two fits for each galaxy.

We preprocess the dataset before we train our model on it. First, we only select galaxies with redshift $z < 1$ because SNe beyond this limit are unlikely to be observed and properties of high z galaxies are likely poorly constrained. Second, we match the bands from each survey based on their approximate median effective wavelength. For example, the R band for ELAIS-S1, W-CDF-S, and XMM-LSS come from DES, VOICE, and HSC, but we approximate them as the same because the impact on our performance will be negligible. We also remove the U band because it is unobserved in W-CDF-S. Third, if there is more than one catalog with observations in one band, we use the catalog with fewer missing observations for that band. Fourth, we only consider galaxies for which we have greater than 8 photometric measurements and all the derived properties, leaving us with 182,761 galaxies ($\sim 16\%$ of the catalog). Finally, we use k -nearest neighbors (KNN) imputation, a method that replaces missing datapoints with the mean of the closest k values, with $k = 5$ to account for missing values; this method should be able to capture some extra information encoded by the host galaxy, as the brightness of different wavelengths is typically correlated. Henceforth, we will refer to this dataset “the galaxy dataset” or “the host dataset”.

2.1.2. Supernovae Catalog

We use the Open Astronomy Catalogs API (OACAPI) (Guillochon & Cowperthwaite 2018) to retrieve a compiled dataset of SNe. The catalog contains photometric values, coordinates, classifications, host information, and a number of other facts about the SNe. The dataset contains 82,605 SNe, 17,319 of which are classified. There are 965 SNe in the DDFs that we focus on, 586 of which are classified, and $\sim 75\%$ of the classified are type Ia. Henceforth, we will refer to this dataset as “the supernova dataset”.

2.1.3. Cone Search

We match our SNe to their hosts with a cone search using the Astropy (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2022) software. For each SN in the SN dataset, we find the galaxy with the minimum angular separation in the galaxy dataset. If smallest angular separation is $< 30''$, we label the galaxy as the host of the SN. While we acknowledge that there are more robust routines for host association, some such as Gagliano et al. (2021) take $\gtrsim 1$ minute per SN so are

Figure 2. The pair-wise relationship between the host stellar mass, star formation rate, redshift, and angular separation between host and SN for all SNe in our dataset. The data are color coded by SN class, and the distributions of the different predictors are displayed along the diagonal.

not preferred for datasets of this size. That being said, we plan to improve this process going forward by calculating association probabilities between the SNe and proposed hosts. We are able to associate 289 of our SNe with hosts from the galaxy dataset with $z < 1$. 82.0% of these SNe are type Ia.

Figure 2, shows the distributions of host galaxy properties and host-SN angular separation, as well as their pairwise relationships for type Ia, type II, and “other” types of SNe. We observe some clustering of supernova type. Visually, redshift seems to be the most correlated feature with SN class, as non-type Ia SNe tend to be at lower redshifts. This may be a result of type Ia being the brightest, and thus the most observable at farther distances. The angular separation between the host and event also appears to have a strong correlation with SN class, as on average type II SNe appear to occur farther from their hosts than type Ia. Finally, type Ia SNe have a relatively wide dispersion of mass and SFR, while type II appears to be tightly clustered around the average values. While there appears to be *some* clustering of the supernova types in host property feature space, we expect stronger correlations. In particular, the hosts of type II SNe are generally understood to have higher SFRs than other types.

2.2. Neural Network

We use a multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network (NN) to infer the properties of SN hosts. MLPs are comprised of an input layer, multiple hidden layers, and an output layer. The interconnected layers which possess unique, non-linear activation functions enable MLPs to model complex relationships, making them effective for classification, regression, and pattern recognition tasks. Their ability to learn from data through backpropagation renders them relatively efficient at performing gradient descent, which has made them one of the preferred tools for solving a wide range of computational problems in recent years.

In this study, we use a MLP to infer host properties from multi-wavelength photometry. We split our galaxy dataset into 80% train and 20% test sets. We train the model by feeding in the photometry measurements from our train set and conducting gradient descent to minimize a loss function (defined below) that compares the NN’s predicted galaxy attributes to Zou et al. (2022)’s derived values.

Figure 3a shows the architecture of our MLP which we implement with the PyTorch (Paszke et al. 2019a) package. We have an 18-node input layer (corresponding to the 18 measured photometric bands), followed by 6 hidden layers with rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation functions, two hidden linear layers, and a linear output layer with 3 nodes corresponding to inferred stellar mass, SFR, and photo- z . The number of nodes in the hidden layers can be found in Figure 3a, and are chosen by taking the model with the minimum test error from a grid search. The linear hidden

Figure 3. (a) The architecture of our multilayer perceptron neural network. Each layer is represented by a block with an arrow pointing at and away from it, representing the input and outputs, respectively. The number in parenthesis in each block is the number of nodes in the layer. We input regularized fluxes for 18 wavelengths into the input layer. The output layer produces inferences of 3 host properties (M_* , redshift, and SFR) corresponding to each node. Throughout the network, all adjacent layers are fully connected. (b) The average test and train loss calculated per batch in each epoch for our model’s training. We use early stopping, so include the best epoch with a vertical dashed line to indicate the model parameters that we choose.

layers towards the bottom of the network are included because we found them useful in extending property prediction to lower values than the ReLU function allows.

We conduct hyperparameter tuning using a grid search over batch size, number of epochs, nodes per layer, number of linear output layers, and learning rate. We use the AdamW stochastic optimizer (see the `PyTorch` documentation and [Loshchilov & Hutter \(2019\)](#) for details) with a learning rate of 0.01 to train our model. We use a batch size of 4096 for 1000 epochs and early stopping with a 50 epoch threshold for decreasing test loss. The model’s training history is shown in Figure 3b, in which training stops at the 226th epoch. We use a custom loss function that is an adaptation of mean squared error (MSE) to account for measured uncertainty,

$$\text{Loss}(\mathbf{y}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{1}{\sigma_i} (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (1)$$

where i is the index of properties for a galaxy, y_i is the i th true derived property, \hat{y}_i the i th predicted derived property, and σ_i is the uncertainty of the i th derived property. Per [Zou et al. \(2022\)](#), the uncertainty on our photo- z s is calculated with

$$\sigma_z = \frac{1}{2} (z_{\max} - z_{\min}) \quad (2)$$

where z_{\max} and z_{\min} are the given upper and lower bounds for the photo- z values, respectively. Assuming that spectroscopic errors are negligible, we set the spectroscopic errors to an arbitrarily small value.

2.3. Random Forest

To classify SNe, we train a random forest (RF) to predict class given NN-inferred host M_* , SFR, and redshift values along with the host-SN angular separation. Random forests are an ensemble learning method known for their robustness in handling complex datasets. By constructing a large number of decision trees and aggregating their outputs, they achieve high accuracy while mitigating overfitting. RFs are favored among classification methods for their efficiency on large datasets and interpretability.

We use a relatively simple RF model from the `scikit-learn` package ([Pedregosa et al. 2011](#)) comprised of 1000 trees. Using 5-fold cross validation we tune the maximum depth of our trees to 12. To train our model, we adopt the

Gini impurity as our loss function, defined by

$$\text{Gini}(Q_m) = \sum_k p_{km}(1 - p_{km}) \quad (3)$$

where Q_m is the data at node m and p_{mk} is the proportion of class k observations in node m .

We use stratified k -fold cross validation to evaluate the accuracy of our model. This method splits data into k parts while ensuring each split has a similar class distribution. Then it iterates through the folds, using one part of the data is for testing and the rest for training the model. This process repeats k times, allowing each part to be a test set once to provide a comprehensive and unbiased assessment of the RF’s performance across different samples. Furthermore, to overcome the type Ia supernova imbalance in our supernova dataset, we use Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE) resampling on our train set, a method in which artificial samples of underrepresented classes are injected into the set by sampling from the lines between datapoints.

2.4. Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the performance of our pipeline, we use a number of metrics that describe prediction and classification accuracy. We will define these metrics below, and describe their use.

The error and fractional error for our models are

$$\text{Error} = |y_{\text{pred}} - y_{\text{obs}}| \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Fractional Error} = \left| \frac{y_{\text{pred}} - y_{\text{obs}}}{\max(y_{\text{pred}}, y_{\text{obs}})} \right| \quad (5)$$

where y_{pred} is the predicted property and $y_{\text{obs},i}$ is the observed/derived property. We calculate error for our test set to find how far our predicted values are from the true values, and use fractional error to adjust for the magnitude of the values that we are predicting. Note that we use the max of the predicted and observed values in the denominator of Equation 5 to account for near-zero floating point errors causing the expression to blowup.

The root mean squared error (RMSE) of a set of predictions is

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{error}^2}{N}} \quad (6)$$

where N is the size of our test set and error is define in Equation 4. We use RMSE to compare the relative uncertainty of our predictions to the uncertainty in the true values—specifically, we can compare this value to the measured uncertainty divided by the measured value to get a sense of if our model’s performance is in line with how uncertain the data are.

To evaluate our classification, we will use stratified k -fold cross validation described in 2.3. To overcome the $\sim 82\%$ type Ia supernova imbalance in our supernova dataset, we use SMOTE, which is detailed in [Chawla et al. \(2002\)](#). We take the mean purity. Purity and completeness (which are used interchangeably with precision and recall in the literature) are defined by

$$\text{Purity} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Completeness} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (8)$$

where TP is true positive, FP is false positive, and FN is false negative for a set of class inferences. Additionally, the accuracy is the number of correct predictions divided by the total number of predictions.

Finally, to compare our pipeline’s performance to other classifiers, we will calculate the F1 score. F1 score is defined as

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2}{\text{completeness}^{-1} + \text{purity}^{-1}} \quad (9)$$

where purity and completeness are defined in Equation 7 and Equation 8, respectively. The F1 score, which is the harmonic mean of a classifier’s purity and completeness, is a metric of a classifier’s accuracy. Values can range from 0.0 being worst to 1.0 being a perfect classification performance.

Figure 4. The real versus predicted values of the stellar mass, star formation rate, and redshift for our 252,326-galaxy test set. Although the network treats photo- z s and spec- z s the same, we depict their results differently here to show the differences in their performance. **Top row:** A heatmap of the real versus predicted distribution of the host galaxy properties. The colorbar is in log count. We include a black line with slope 1 that goes through the origin such that if all predictions were exactly correct they would lie on the line. **Bottom row:** The real versus predicted distributions plotted on the same axis as normalized histograms.

3. PIPELINE PERFORMANCE

3.1. Neural Network Performance

Our neural network performs relatively well at predicting properties of host galaxies from their multi-wavelength observations. In Figure 3b we show the training history of the model in which it achieves a minimum test error of 1.82 with a train error of 1.90 on a 80 – 20 train-test split of the galaxy dataset. In Figure 4, we show the true versus NN-predicted scatters and distributions for M_* , SFR, photo- z , and spec- z in the test set for our host galaxies. In the top row, for all properties besides photo- z we observe a very concentrated density around the “perfect” prediction values—the counts near the black lines appear more than an order of magnitude greater than elsewhere.

There are, however a few obvious issues with the performance of our neural network. First, there appears to be both low M_* and low SFR groups that our NN struggles to predict. These low-valued galaxies are a result of highly uncertain photo- z s in the galaxy dataset. The vast majority of the low-mass and low-SFR tails of our training set has photometrically inferred redshifts, which can suffer from substantially higher uncertainties. This suggests that the redshift values for the low-valued tails may be incorrect, leading to poor constraints on galaxy properties due to degeneracies in the SED fits from Zou et al. (2022).

The low M_* and SFR bumps lead to the second obvious shortcoming of the NN performance, which is the relatively poor inference of photo- z s. Considering that the shading is in log-scale, there does seem to be a considerable density of photo- z inferences around their true values; this is, however, obviously the weakest correlation, which we attribute to the photo- z measurements having large uncertainties. Accurate photo- z values are notoriously difficult to obtain, and their poorly constrained values make it difficult for the NN to make accurate inferences. In fact, we can even see the grid search SED fitting methodology used by Zou et al. (2022) in the form of vertical stripes in the photo- z scatter plot. On the other hand, the NN performs exceedingly well with spec- z s, producing high-accuracy predictions for nearly all the host galaxies. The uncertainties on spec- z s are effectively zero, so the high accuracy of these inferences leads us to believe that the network has the potential to accurately infer photo- z s given better constraints. There is a

Statistic	Fractional Error			Error			Measured Uncertainties		
	$\log(M_*)$	$\log(\text{SFR})$	z	$\log(M_*)$	$\log(\text{SFR})$	z	$\log(M_*)$	$\log(\text{SFR})$	z
Mean	0.0333	0.2233	0.1436	0.4092	0.6015	0.1436	0.1839	0.3254	1.4333
Median	0.0173	0.1339	0.1050	0.2121	0.3607	0.105	0.1626	0.2399	0.5543
Stdev	0.0466	0.2781	0.1363	0.5722	0.7491	0.1363	0.1020	0.2865	1.9451
Other Metrics									
Metric	$\log(M_*)$			$\log(\text{SFR})$			z		
Prediction RMSE	0.7035			0.9607			0.1980		
Measured (Uncertainty)/(Value)	0.3975			0.2510			0.8293		

Table 1. Summary metrics of the neural network performance. We show the error (Eq. 4), fractional error (Eq. 5), and RMSE (Eq. 6) for the host properties inferred by our neural net. Note the Eq. 5 is a variation of fractional error used to account for floating point issues. We include measured uncertainties and measured uncertainty divided by true value magnitude for reference.

sharp cutoff in the predictions at $z \sim 0.9$, which may be a result of the poor data resulting from treating both redshift types the same.

The performance metrics listed in Table 1 also indicate that our network produces relatively accurate predictions. We see a median fractional error (defined in Eq. 5 as a variation of fractional error for computational reasons) of 0.017, 0.1339, and 0.1050 for $\log(M_*)$, $\log(\text{SFR})$, and z , respectively. The RMSEs for these values are 0.704, 0.251, and 0.899, and the ratio between measured uncertainty and value are 0.398, 0.251, and 0.829, respectively. These metrics are comparable descriptions of uncertainty in the observed and true values, so the fact that they are similar in magnitude suggests that our model performs well given the uncertainty on the true values themselves.

3.2. Random Forest Performance

Our random forest classifier achieves a mean of 79% and 53% accuracy at classifying the validation set type Ia and non-type Ia SNe in stratified k -fold cross validation with $k = 50$ and 289 SNe (see Section 2.3 for the specifics of our methodology). The left side of Figure 5 shows the confusion matrix for this cross validation. We observed that the random forest model performs very similarly when using NN-inferred and derived properties, as the classifiers achieves $\sim 40\%$ and $\sim 90\%$ purity for the non-Ia and Ia SNe classes, respectively. The similarity in class inferences using NN-inferred and true host properties is an encouraging proof-of-concept for NN half of the pipeline because it shows that our inferred properties capture the same information that the true properties do.

As is shown on the right side for Figure 5, the purity of classifications can be improved by cutting down on sample completeness. In fact, for 0.2 completeness, the model classifies type Ia with 100% purity and non-Ia with $\sim 55\%$ using NN-inferred *or* derived properties. Furthermore, the model appears to perform equally well with the true or inferred data for all levels of completeness, once again validating the pipeline leading up to the random forest.

To see whether the intermediate step of inferring galaxy properties improves our pipeline’s performance, we compare the results of our pipeline to a RF that infers SN class by taking host SEDs as input. The mean F1 score (defined in Equation 9 from the 50-fold cross validation performed for Figure 5 is 0.834 ± 0.119 . For a RF that takes host SEDs as input, the F1 score is 0.816 ± 0.123 . Therefore, although inferring galaxy properties as an intermediary step grounds the pipeline’s predictions in intuitive, physical terms, it does not actually improve the performance of the classifier. We discuss this result in the following section, but note that it does not mean that host property inference is a useless step in our pipeline—as is mentioned in Section 1, the pipeline still offers greater utility than an SED-based classifier because it enables scientists to select for the demographics of the environments of SNe populations that they study.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1. Classification Performance and Improvement Prospects

The purity and accuracy achieved by the pipeline summarized in Figure 5 are not quite at the level of cutting edge SN classification techniques. One of the foremost use cases for this pipeline is classifying SNe very early in their lives in order to identify candidates for follow up; so, purity is of primary importance, as misclassifications cost instrument time. Existing methods often achieve purity statistics $> 50\%$ for type II SNe (see Qu et al. (2021); Gagliano et al. (2021)) which comprise the majority of the non-Ia SNe in the supernova dataset. Our pipeline generally produces

Figure 5. The classification performance of our random forest based on 50-fold cross validation. **Left:** The confusion matrix of our predictions. Each square in the grid shows the mean purity achieved with our NN during stratified k-fold cross validation with $k = 50$. The number of SNe in each class is included in parenthesis. The top and bottom triangles correspond to the performance using NN-inferred and derived properties, respectively. **Right:** The purity versus completeness plot of classifications for type Ia and other SNe. Again, we include the classifications from both the NN-inferred host properties, as well as the true properties. Finally, the two black lines represent the portions of the populations in our sets that are type Ia and other.

accurate predictions of SN host properties, and the RF performs extremely similarly when trained on inferred or true host properties; these two facts mean that the RF is largely the source of misclassification in the proposed pipeline.

We posit that our pipeline performs worse than existing classification routines as a result of having an insufficient dataset—there are only 286 SNe in the dataset that are classified, have derived properties, and can be associated with a host, 52 of which are not Ia. Even with using SMOTE in training, the data are likely too imbalanced for a random forest to accurately learn the feature space. The minimal effects of SMOTE are somewhat unsurprising, as oversampling is not known to be very impactful for RFs performance. The lack of robustness of the SN dataset is underscored by the unexpectedly poor clustering of host properties in Figure 2, specifically with respect to the correlation between SFR and SN class. Furthermore, Gagliano et al. (2021) was able to achieve better performance with a random forest using true galaxy properties, confirming that the data are lacking, not the model complexity.

To improve our model’s performance, we will look to add domain adaptation to our pipeline in the form of a neural network that predicts IR and UV bands given the optical. Doing so would enable us to associate our SN dataset with galaxies in the Pan-STARRS (Flewelling et al. 2020) catalog, which contains over 16,000 optically observed SNe and hosts galaxies. Also, LSST plans to take photometric measurements only in the *grizy* bands, so this makes our model immediately useful for when the Vera A. Rubin Observatory goes online.

With a more robust dataset, we would also look forward to understanding whether the intermediate step of inferring host galaxy properties aids in SN classification. While Section 3.2 shows that an SED-based classifier seems to have very similar performance to our pipeline, it is very possible that this may not be the case when our pipeline is exposed to more data. Furthermore, it is possible that the additional step of inferring host properties improves classification for sources where the data are only from *grizy* bands, as fewer photometric measurements may lead to accurate host property predictions, but not SNe class inferences.

4.2. Anomalous Supernova Detection

In terms of future work, a host-property based supernova classification would be valuable for anomalous SN detection. The demographics of rare SNe are poorly constrained in large part due to lack of observations. By inferring host properties with our pipeline, scientists can select on interpretable host features for interesting or anomalous transients. With the onset of an unprecedented number of transient detections that will come from the Vera C. Rubin Observatory, a tool like this pipeline is crucial for rapidly identifying the “needle in the haystack” SNe for observational follow up.

4.3. Inference of Photo-zs

Our neural network achieves a median photo- z test error and fractional error of 0.111 and 0.184, respectively. Obtaining the redshift values of galaxies is essential for large-scale cosmological studies, and thus has been the focus of a number of studies (e.g. Henghes et al. (2022)). In fact, studies have developed methods to rapidly infer photo- z from multi-band observations before. Although our photo- z predictions are more poorly constrained than the other properties (see Figure 4), our photo- z predictions are still a valuable byproduct of this classification pipeline. With a training set that has better constrained photo- z s, our model would likely produce better photo- z estimates, therefore posing an efficient means of mapping the redshifts of large multi-wavelength galaxy catalogs. Furthermore the prospect of implementing domain adaptation to enable an array of wavelength inputs discussed in Section 4.1 would increase the versatility of a deep learning spec- z approach by opening the door to a wide range of photometric catalogs.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study offers a machine learning pipeline for classifying SNe using host galaxy multi-wavelength photometry. We use a multilayer perceptron neural network to infer host stellar mass, star formation rate, and redshift. We input these inferred properties and the SN-host angular separation into a random forest to infer whether the supernova is type Ia or not. Our neural network predicts host galaxy properties quite well, with an average root-mean-squared error of 0.621, which is quite comparable to the observed uncertainties themselves. Our random forest does a fair job at classifying supernovae with their host properties, achieving purities of $\sim 97.5\%$ and $\sim 55\%$ with 20% completeness for type Ia and other supernovae, respectively. While this is not quite cutting edge performance, we seek to improve these metrics by using a more robust, balanced dataset from the Pan-STARRS (Flewelling et al. 2020) catalog, which will in turn make our model capable of classifying SNe from a broad range of catalogs including the LSST.

We thank Xiangang Chen for running Harvard’s Astronomy 98 course in which this work was developed, and for his guidance throughout the process. We appreciate advice, code for SN-host association, and useful feedback from Alex Gagliano. Furthermore, we are grateful to Edo Berger for his helpful critiques on early drafts of the paper. Finally, we thank the FAS research computing group for resources and assistance with the high performance computing aspect of this project.

Software: Python 3.11.5 (Python Core Team 2019), Numpy (Harris et al. 2020), Matplotlib (Hunter 2007), PyTorch (Paszke et al. 2019b), Astropy (Astropy Collaboration et al. 2013, 2018), scikit-learn (Pedregosa et al. 2011), Seaborn (Waskom 2021), Astro GHOST (Gagliano et al. 2021)

REFERENCES

- Astropy Collaboration, Robitaille, T. P., Tollerud, E. J., et al. 2013, *A&A*, 558, A33, doi: [10.1051/0004-6361/201322068](https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201322068)
- Astropy Collaboration, Price-Whelan, A. M., Sipőcz, B. M., et al. 2018, *AJ*, 156, 123, doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/aabc4f](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/aabc4f)
- Astropy Collaboration, Price-Whelan, A. M., Lim, P. L., et al. 2022, *ApJ*, 935, 167, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/ac7c74](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/ac7c74)
- Bostroem, K. A., Pearson, J., Shrestha, M., et al. 2023, Early Spectroscopy and Dense Circumstellar Medium Interaction in SN 2023ixf. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.10119>
- Brammer, G. B., van Dokkum, P. G., & Coppi, P. 2008, *ApJ*, 686, 1503, doi: [10.1086/591786](https://doi.org/10.1086/591786)
- Chawla, N. V., Bowyer, K. W., Hall, L. O., & Kegelmeyer, W. P. 2002, *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research*, 16, 321, doi: [10.1613/jair.953](https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.953)
- Filippenko, A. V. 1997, *ARA&A*, 35, 309, doi: [10.1146/annurev.astro.35.1.309](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.astro.35.1.309)
- Flewelling, H. A., Magnier, E. A., Chambers, K. C., et al. 2020, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 251, 7, doi: [10.3847/1538-4365/abb82d](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/abb82d)
- Gagliano, A., Narayan, G., Engel, A., Carrasco Kind, M., & LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration. 2021, *ApJ*, 908, 170, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/abd02b](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/abd02b)
- Guillochon, J., & Cowperthwaite, P. S. 2018, *Research Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 2, 27, doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/aac2c8](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/aac2c8)
- Harris, C. R., Millman, K. J., van der Walt, S. J., et al. 2020, *Nature*, 585, 357–362, doi: [10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2649-2)
- Henghes, B., Thiyagalingam, J., Pettitt, C., Hey, T., & Lahav, O. 2022, *MNRAS*, 512, 1696, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stac480](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stac480)
- Hunter, J. D. 2007, *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 9, 90, doi: [10.1109/MCSE.2007.55](https://doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2007.55)

- 365 Kelly, P. L., & Kirshner, R. P. 2012, *The Astrophysical*
366 *Journal*, 759, 107, doi: [10.1088/0004-637X/759/2/107](https://doi.org/10.1088/0004-637X/759/2/107)
- 367 Kislely, M., Qin, Y.-J., Zabludoff, A., Barnard, K., & Ko,
368 C.-L. 2023, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 942, 29,
369 doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/aca532](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/aca532)
- 370 Kulkarni, S. R. 2020, *Towards An Integrated Optical*
371 *Transient Utility*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2004.03511>
- 372 Loshchilov, I., & Hutter, F. 2019, *Decoupled Weight Decay*
373 *Regularization*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.05101>
- 374 LSST Science Collaboration, Abell, P. A., Allison, J., et al.
375 2009, arXiv e-prints, arXiv:0912.0201,
376 doi: [10.48550/arXiv.0912.0201](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.0912.0201)
- 377 Ni, Q., Brandt, W. N., Chen, C.-T., et al. 2021, *ApJS*, 256,
378 21, doi: [10.3847/1538-4365/ac0dc6](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ac0dc6)
- 379 Paszke, A., Gross, S., Massa, F., et al. 2019a, in *Advances*
380 *in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Vol. 32,
381 8026–8037
- 382 Paszke, A., Gross, S., Massa, F., et al. 2019b, *PyTorch: An*
383 *Imperative Style, High-Performance Deep Learning*
384 *Library*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/1912.01703>
- 385 Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., et al. 2011,
386 *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 12, 2825
- 387 Python Core Team. 2019, *Python: A dynamic, open source*
388 *programming language*, Python Software Foundation.
389 <https://www.python.org/>
- 390 Qu, H., Sako, M., Möller, A., & Doux, C. 2021, *AJ*, 162, 67,
391 doi: [10.3847/1538-3881/ac0824](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-3881/ac0824)
- 392 Waskom, M. L. 2021, *Journal of Open Source Software*, 6,
393 3021, doi: [10.21105/joss.03021](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.03021)
- 394 Yang, G., Boquien, M., Buat, V., et al. 2020, *MNRAS*, 491,
395 740, doi: [10.1093/mnras/stz3001](https://doi.org/10.1093/mnras/stz3001)
- 396 Zhu, J., Jiang, N., Dong, S., et al. 2023, *The Astrophysical*
397 *Journal*, 949, 23, doi: [10.3847/1538-4357/acc2c3](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4357/acc2c3)
- 398 Zou, F., Yang, G., Brandt, W. N., et al. 2021, *Research*
399 *Notes of the American Astronomical Society*, 5, 56,
400 doi: [10.3847/2515-5172/abf050](https://doi.org/10.3847/2515-5172/abf050)
- 401 Zou, F., Brandt, W. N., Chen, C.-T., et al. 2022, *The*
402 *Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 262, 15,
403 doi: [10.3847/1538-4365/ac7bdf](https://doi.org/10.3847/1538-4365/ac7bdf)